

CULTIVATION OF PSALMS IN ROMANIAN LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE LESSONS – AN ALTERNATIVE METHOD OF EDUCATING STUDENTS' LITERARY-RELIGIOUS CONSCIOUSNESS

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Abstract. *Romanian religious poetry, the psalm, falling out emotionally or just semantic (literally) has been cultivated since the earliest times, is the most ancient literary species, educating the masses, inserting and maintaining the religious thrill from the earliest age. In Romanian Language and Literature classes, it can be cultivated as an alternative method of receiving a lyrical text, a text of the highest literary quality. They can be used as shield texts, to accustom the reader to the reception of a lyrical text and to create that IF condition that induces the reader an involved and conscious attitude.*

Keywords: *religious poetry, psalm, religious thrill, literary-religious consciousness, Romanian language and literature lessons, lyrical text.*

CULTIVAREA PSALMILOR ÎN CADRUL LECȚIILOR DE LIMBA ȘI LITERATURA ROMÂNĂ – METODĂ ALTERNATIVĂ DE EDUCARE A CONȘTIINȚEI LITERAR-RELIGIOASE A ELEVILOR

Rezumat. *Poezia religioasă românească, în care psalmul se încadrează din punct de vedere emoțional și semantic (etimologic), a fost cultivată încă din cele mai îndepărtate timpuri. E specia literară cu cea mai mare vechime, care educă masele, inoculează și menține fiorul religios de la cele mai fragede vârste. La lecțiile de limba și literatura română, psalmii pot reprezenta o metodă alternativă de receptare a textelor lirice de cea mai înaltă ținută literară. Poezia creștină românească de inspirație biblică contribuie la educarea conștiinței literar-religioase a elevilor.*

Cuvinte-cheie: *poezie religioasă, psalm, fior religios, conștiință literar-religioasă, lecții de limba și literatura română, text liric.*

Christianity has a *Creed* and a *Gospel*. Art has aesthetic and moral ideals, which unites it with religion and this connection was made through the Word. Words united in lyrics, words united in music, words united in colors.

No one doubts the significance and benefits of art, just as no one doubts the significance and benefits of religion. Their contribution to taming morals, brightening their foreheads, and educating people is impressive.

In order to caress, rejoice and feel the thrills of happiness, from time immemorial, man sings,

paints, models, builds, dances, listens or makes lyrics and music, but he also prays to the divinity.

Gathering together all the arts and all the masterpieces of mankind, all that human genius could create more valuable we will have before us pagodas, sphinxes, obelisks, temples and cathedrals, paintings, statues and sacred monuments, all primarily of a religious nature.

Poetry, music, architecture, sculpture, painting, dance, first had a religious content. None of the historical religions has maintained a more fruitful collaboration with art than Christianity has. Thus,

the most precious book that history has passed and will pass without harm at all appears in the heart of a Christian people, the first in the history of mankind, a book considered both history, literature, myth or fantasy [1, p. 231].

The „Bible” – the history of the Christianization of a the people has in its real pages of fiction, a timid fiction of course and what makes us admit this are some of his books, such as: *Song of Songs, Ecclesiastes and especially the Psalms of King David*.

Written in the moments of repentance or soul satisfaction, of silent adoration or humiliation, the number of Davidic psalms is 151 and some were created by King David in gratitude that God did not punish him with death for the (indirect, but wilful) murder of Uriah Hete, in order to take his wife. Through the prophet Nathan, David obtains God's forgiveness, but as a punishment, the son born of this bond dies immediately after birth.

Full of repentance, the prophet and King David wrote hymns to Yahweh, whose beauty was interpreted by the contribution of great and important churchmen, to the Romanians the first interpreter and versifier of the Psalter, being Metropolitan Dosoftei of Moldavia.

Although timid at the time, the Romanian literary language finds a special intertwining with the popular one and the translation resulting from the colossal work of Metropolitan Dosoftei is a smooth one, gently caressing the ear of the Christian absorbed in holy service or the fervent reader seeking God. In Dosoftei's translation, the Psalm of David, as it is titled in the opening of the work, sounds promising and laudatory: „Blessed is the man who does not walk / On the advice of the lawless / And the worst will not stand in the way / Not even sitting in a losing seat / He will also be with the Lord with his will / And in his law he slept.”

But in addition to the promises of good for the righteous, the last verses of the psalm bring to the fore the heathen who do not follow the right path, and those will be cooked as the parable says, „the place of everlasting darkness” where it will be crying and gnashing of teeth: „That the Lord sees the righteous / All the way from the sitting chair. / And the crooked way of the heathen / He will perish and fall into abomination.”

We notice that Metropolitan Dosoftei transformed the psalms per Romanian meter and with rhymes taken from popular poetry, introducing over the authentic content of the original a lot of elements of observation, a lot of other loans, which come from the very life of the Romanian people, thus reaching

to things of great beauty, which do not even need any correction to please even today.

Going through Dosoftei's Psalter is like a journey through a land of poetic wonders. For example, in *Psalm 9* we are amazed by that solemn-bitter portrait of the sinner, which culminates in two lapidary verses, like an inscription carved in the slab of words: „Her mouth is full of bitterness / Blasphemy, blasphemy and deceit [2, p. 654]!

The lamentation of the one who feels abandoned by the Lord is built in the biblical spirit, but the metaphors have a concreteness that does not exist in the holy book: „And my bones were torn / My heart is breaking / Like a wax when it melts / My virtue is like a sack cloth, / The tongue in the gums stuck to drowning.” (*Psalm 21*).

What is remarkable is the simplicity of the moral, inner verse of the lyrical confession: „As a mourner who mourns his dead / I am sad, Lord, and utterly grieved.” (*Psalm 36*) *Psalm 50*, so sung and recited in the Orthodox Churches, translated as, „Have mercy on me, O God, according to thy great mercy, and according to the multitude of thy tender mercies, cleanse my iniquity,” reads Dosoftei's verse as follows: „Have mercy on me, Lord, for forgive me, / With the rich mercy, / And for your infinity / Cleanse me from wickedness.”

„Thou shalt sprinkle with hyssop, and I shall be clean: yea, I shall be whiter than snow,” sang the Emperor the prophet, and Dosoftei translates: „It simply came to my notice then / And it clears me of the mistake.”

In his translation, Dosoftei always knew how to find the exact correspondences, understood the metaphors and interpreted them through happy equivalences [3, p. 754]. Original and full of concrete details, it expresses the thirst for God of body and soul. Drying, twisting the body, as in waste without water, is especially memorable: [2, p. 656] „That many times he wants you, / The body, the squirrel squirms, / Can deserted and dry, / No water and no ironing.” (*Psalm 62*).

In another psalm, we see the fatigue, the compulsion, which fills the prayer with a willow water and in which a motif very similar to the Paschal one of the abysses is translated into an Arghegian lexicon: „Oh, Holy God, you take me out / The water, the crowds, / What comes to my mind and bullets / Like deep mists, without bridges / That I am surrounded by the depths / If the ivory pulls at me, / Screaming made me dizzy / They silenced my tongue in toil ...” (*Psalm 68*)

The ease with which they are uttered, the images created and the inner rhyme of the verses reminiscent of popular Romanian poetry have made Dosoftei's poetry, his psalms, true religious hymns. Some of his psalms are known from the outside, being collected by Anton Pann, becoming carols, entitled Star Songs, for example: „At the water of the Vavilon, / Wailing for the Land of the Lord, / There we sit and cry / At the crown we gather ... (Psalm 36).

How many times have they not mourned in our hardest years, when many are torn from their hearths, gone elsewhere or far away, when many could not imagine the time to return to the hearth victorious Romanian soldiers? How many times did the psalm resound in their souls: „If only we could look at you, / Jerusalem city!”

This is also the state of the Sadovian characters, who, even knowing the biblical songs, mourned with bitter tears, a lovely woman left at home, a tearful wife and children hungry for the burden of mastery.

The presence of a biblical-religious vein in the Sadovian works is indisputable, the volumes *Tears of the Hieromonk Veniamin, Towards Emmaus, Holy Legends* etc. indicating this, albeit a little vaguely. But after 1930, this vein gained a considerable share at all levels of the work, starting with *Maria Sa Puil Pădurii* and going to the real prose poems represented by litany sequences from *Hunting Stories, Wolf's Island, The People of His Majesty* [5, p. 98].

From here to the actual poetry was only a step and Mihail Sadoveanu would do it exactly during the elaboration of the works *The Persian Divan, The People of His Majesty, The Jderi Brothers*. The intermediate link was the work of translating the psalms, a work to which he dedicated a long period of elaboration, culminating with „Prayers” in the manner of the psalms, entitled *Lyrical Creations in the manner of the psalms*.

Although the Sadovian psalms are higher than those of Dosoftei considering the musicality of the verses, as well as the lexicon used due to the fact that the language was at its maturity, the Sadovian prayers are more interesting; starting with the first entitled *For Grief*, Sadoveanu draws up a real prayer book that seems to be intended for the soldier on the front and read in the silence of the tent, before the battle: „Blessed be he in all the days of the Lord / The one who carries our burden. / God, master of the world, I rise up to you, / You are my refuge.”

In the same way the psalm number two continues, entitled *For the Sorrowful Heart*, where the author asks for mercy to the divinity and help every day, his hope being only in Him. After beginning with

the invocation of the deity, the psalmist shows what his sins are but also his innocence, praying like Lot once to save him from perdition and eternal punishment: “I hate the sobs of the wicked / And among the wicked I did not go. / I will always walk in your righteousness. / Deliver me, have mercy on me / For from you alone, Lord, my hope is Friday / Amen.”

Psalm three, entitled For the Soldier in the Straits, begins with a praise to God for the world and its accomplishments. In the last part, the soldier asks for forgiveness, afraid of his nothingness and sinfulness, but also deliverance from the enemies of the country. Isn't this Stefanita's prayer before dealing with the pagan armies? : „My Lord, who warms me strongly / The enemies scattered; / Those who hate us are dust. / The enemies of my Lord have fallen / And on his forehead will shine the crown of victory. / Amen!”

Doesn't this image bring Moses and Joshua to the battle with the Amalekites when Moses stands with his hands raised to defeat the enemies of his Lord?

As for the following psalm – *For the country* – we can say that it continues in the same laudatory register, here praising in the first part the benefits done in the author's country: “Country with rivers and forests, plains and seas, / A rich country among all the countries of the world, / She was destined for us, you were part of us. / The land which the Lord cares for.”

And in the last part of the psalm we meet the prayer of request that the psalmist makes in order to obtain the divine blessing on his country, asking for his support against the enemies.

Psalm number five, *For the King*, contains like the other two parts: one for the glorification of divine deeds, for creation, and one for prayer, a prayer made by soldiers invoking God's blessing and asking them to make the ruler wise and deliver them: „Please, O Lord, and bless the king's house / And blessed be the house of our king forever. / Amen.”

The last creation in this cycle is a prayer for the death of the brave who, at the hour of death, entrusts his soul to the creator, resigned and praying to place him in the army of the righteous, given his brave deeds: „Lord, end the death of the righteous, / Their end to be theirs / ... / Lord of spirits, add my soul / In the fog of your soldiers, next to you. / Amen.”

The Sadovian psalms or his prayers in a psalmic way are created in white verse, which gives him the same freedom of expression that the thread of thoughts dictates. Although they have an inner rhythm, they are somewhat devoid of the specific

musicality imposed on the church songs brought in his creations by Macedonski.

Due to his symbolist nature, Macedonski manages to assert himself on this level of religious literature, creating a series of eleven psalms from which the idea derived from the reader has the bitter taste of vanity of vanities.

The first of this series is a lament on the theme of the ephemerality of man, who, even if he has an immortal soul, cries after the carnal covering, so handsome in sight, but so subject to time and the passage of time. As Eminescu said in his thoughts – „Every man is a question asked of man to the spirit of the Universe”, Macedonski calls it a song, but a sad one, which ends too quickly: „Dry is all that has blossomed, / Enthusiasm is dead / And my heart froze ... / I was a passing song / And I'm a song.”

„Dust ... we are all dust / Any arrogance is superfluous ... / What was, will forever be ... / Nothing will remain of us”, he continues in the same sad tone, the author elegiac starting from to the biblical idea of creation: „From dust we are made, and from dust we return.”

Continuing in a deliberately weeping tone, the poet creates an image reminiscent of the first part of Letter I, revealing once again the futility of life and the omnipotence of fate: „Despots with crowned foreheads, / Poets with crowned harps, / Philosophers, scientists, / Pagans, made known by unbelief / No loss is postponed ... / Dust, we are all dust.”

With the following psalm – *Forgiveness* – the poet changes the register by faithfully describing the condition of the man who, when he feels the burden of life or a little sadness, thinks he is persecuted by everyone, forgetting that he is still the son of God: „Forgiveness! I'm like any human being. / I'm the bastard over whom / If there is a sadness / Everyone is persecuted, / But, God, you didn't leave me / I am a man like any other man – forgiveness!”

The same invocation of divine help is found in the *Enemies*, but also in *I was flying*, where the poet asks for shelter away from sins, in the courts of Eden mourning at the same time the age of naivety, of innocent childhood when: „I was flying on bright wings ... / The old boy / Innocent as a girl / Undaunted by temptations, / It's muddy mud today.”

But the resistance of the one on the cross, but also of the afflicted man is glorified with elegiac accents in I said to myself: „Brothers, relatives, they all hated me, / The more I cried, the more they grinned. / An entire country has passed / Give me poison and I drank it. / But God, they didn't beat you.”

Returning to futility, however, the poet expresses it sadly in „How hard I worked, how much I worked / And now I did not use.”, But also in I have no star in the heavens, where the dominant theme is expressed by what it means the term „apathea”, as in the Eminescu *Glossa*: „I live in the world for no purpose! / I'm just a name, / I don't cry anymore, I don't moan anymore.”

Or perhaps it is that abandonment in the care of the Lord, when the weary fighting spirit finds no power of rebellion against the injustices of fate: „When you give cruelty to the wicked, / Give meekness to the victims. / You are the wise power / And righteous justice; / Do whatever you want with me at any time / God, they are all through You ... ”

Finally, the author of the *Nights* returns to his original tone, proving once again that everything is „vanitas vanitatum”, revealing himself as a faithful admirer of the *Ecclesiastes*:

„Wealth, poverty / It's all in vain / Health, youth / Mind, soul, beauty, / Everything that was, what is going to be, / It's all in vain / Be, live, but do not want ... ”

Always fashionable, so never considered obsolete, *The Ecclesiastes* was a source of inspiration for the literati of the times, as was *the Psalms*. At the beginning of this chapter I was wondering why this longevity of the genre? Why so many psalmic drops throughout the creations of authors who do not even have a religious character in their lyrics? Why did Bacovia choose to write a poem and call it *Psalm* when it has nothing to do with what the word means in etymology? Why just one, scattered and awkward?

He might as well have titled his poem *Hymn to the Beloved*, but probably, as we know, master of shocking images, intrigues once again by the title chosen in contrast to the words used. Intrigued by the fact that everyone, when they hear the word psalm uttered, makes contact with the layman; the explanation is simple, however – the poem itself is a psalm, one dedicated to the beloved, expressing the consistency of feelings and unwavering adoration: „Honey, with a dead face, / Crazy genius, / Monotonous, / Naked Madonna, / Dusty lilies / I carry you in my dream.”

The sacred register is combined with shocking elements from the sphere of the layman, and the persistence of feelings is expressed by repeating the verse „In my dream I carry you”, which concludes all three stanzas of poetry, while giving a deliberately slow, ritualistic rhythm. But the Bacovian lover, pure and splendid as the lilies of the field, remains

mute and inaccessible „like the cold marble”, so that even her existence is questioned, not materializing in any of her poems. It is like the Arghezian God to whom the poet in the Psalmist confesses: „The soul prays on its knees on the bare stone: / "Get rid of me, Father, at least in doubt."

A cry beyond time ... a cry beyond words ... mourning and stubborn searching...Arghezi. The most prolific psalmist, but also the most interesting in Romanian literature. When you say psalm, you say Arghezi, even if in the course of time the psalms meant something else.

Evolving from a purely biblical philosophy, in Arghezi's hand the psalm becomes an entity, it becomes a river flowing with questions, requests, but also of dedication, damnation, but also of glorification, repentance, but also of rebellion. It becomes a nebula of feelings enclosed in a psalm hourglass. The harp becomes useless in so much musicality that slips through the lyrics.

With Arghezi, the psalm is something else: he is not only the man who praises the Creator, he is the man who wants more, who manifests his luciferic side, even with the fear of being punished. With him, the psalm becomes poetry, not just a litany, although Macedonski tries the same thing.

With Arghezi the psalm becomes complicated philosophy and literary genre. Read in chronological order, the poems of the Psalms describe a „circle” of Arghezian mysticism, choosing the two consecrated forms of thought: one that seeks the interpretation of God by rational means and one that proposes intuitive knowledge, through mystical ecstasy. Arghezi, undecided, however, chooses the latter, anxiously seeking to know who He is in himself. [8, pag. 243]

Arghezi seems to be part of the family of healers, of the seekers of ultimate, sublime essences, of elixirs and filters, but not of that of priests or apostles. In the Middle Ages, it would have been burned alive. He is closer to Dr. Faust than to St. d'Assise [6, p.156].

If in the seventeenth century, Dosoftei had autochthonized in Romanian poetry the language of Christian veneration and obedience, Arghezi uses it, giving him not only new powers, but also increasing the complexity of the language of faith, adding his denial, whose appearance would have been impossible [7, p. 149].

This is what distinguishes Arghezi in literature of this kind, although the language of veneration and obedience remains dominant; predominant is the tone of prayer and in one of the psalms we find

what might be called a meta-prayer: „My prayer is without words, / And the song, Lord, is voiceless. / I'm not asking you for anything. I don't remember anything. / I'm not even an hour away from your eternity." (*My prayer is without words*)

The representative text for the cycle of psalms is I am guilty of coveting. Appeared here, the language of rebellion is subjugated to that of repentance, the beginning and end of the poem indicating confidence in the world order: „But I, in secret of all things, I heard your word that it was impossible.”

The order is made by utterance, that is, of putting into meaning, of uttering things, which is the true fruitfulness of the artist. He confesses, „I missed that God who was neither in books nor in churches and whom people passed by and did not see. I found that one.” [4, p.169]

He did not see him, but found him. Although the search seems doomed, he is happy to search. I would dare say that a concrete result would make him unhappy, hindering the lyrical drama; what imposes him as the greatest poet of faith, according to Mircea Scarlat, is precisely this incomparable talent of search and discovery that sustains the lyrical emotion. As he himself states in the literary survey „Why do you write?” he will search and write incessantly „as long as I can move from one finger and there will be a spark of light and a diopter for my nose ridden by a spectacle”, as long as Arghezi feels that he will not stop writing, searches and questions. So much time!!!

Arghezian through some images in which the notation and the accent are interesting, Barbu Fundoianu makes a poetry of rural inspiration, without being idyllic, in the same measure being interesting also in psalms. What Fundoianu took and processed from Arghezi is only a timid lament, without the power of a real rebellion.

The psalm of the leper in the volume *Priveleşti* opens with a quote from *Leviticus* (13-45) as a motto and is a conglomeration of opposing images, moving from the earthly to the heavenly register, from prayer to humility, from praise to timid reproach :

„Have mercy on me, O Lord, have mercy on me / And, if you can, cleanse me of the disease... / I know, God / That you are safe because I am a leper, / That I came out of nowhere, / That my prostration magnifies you, / That my ignorance gives you knowledge, / That my weakness gives you strength, / That my dirt gives you light.”

The poet does not rebel because he is aware of the presence and existence of God. His God is present insofar as the poet begets him. From the exis-

tence of one arises the existence of the other. The poet is a leper who needs to change his carnal or spiritual attire, so he needs God and then He exists. The author does not question this, but only prays for salvation.

More interesting is the second – the *Psalm of Adam*, in which the tone is more categorical, not just servant, negotiating peace and lost divine love: „I miss you and your beard - / I've forgiven you for so long – you know, / why are you hiding in the rain and storms / when are you in all the bones in me? ”

The reason for the sacrifice for the forgiveness of sin is evident in the last verses, where it falls into a silent adoration edged with a flood of thanksgiving: „Thank you, O Lord, for your mercy. / Thank you for your love, for your mercy, / And that you received, as a sign that you are with us, / The lower sacrifice of my son Abel!”

The tragic man is the template of Barbu Fundoianu's poetry and the only solution he has at hand is to continue to hope, to survive, but also to create poetry.

Poetry ... yes, this is the main motivation for which Ștefan Baciu also writes. In the same literary inquiry, he confesses: „I write because I can't help it: I write because words and thoughts often torment me and pile up in me, and only then I do feel complete and relieved when I see them lying on the paper in front of me.”

Ștefan Baciu, betrayed by his religious bill, also writes psalms (it could not be otherwise), most of his creations being published in the magazine *The Thought*. Feeling connected to the orientation of the magazine given by Nechifor Crainic, he entrusts to the magazine some of his psalms.

In *The Thought* no. 1–3 of May 1936, he published a poem entitled simply *Psalm* and another *Psalm of obedience*. In the first of them, he confesses his desire to be in heaven, finally submitting to the given condition, waiting for his salvation. If in the first part he thanks the divine grace that gave him a being, in the second part of the poem, from the accusation of loneliness, he would like to be hired in heaven for a series of „daily” works:

„It would be better if you held me, God / To drag the wicked into heaven, / To wipe the dust of the shield angels / And to Precista to see them for jewels.”

In the end, he submits to lead his life as he was destined to, seeing in earthly existence the same motive we find in G. Bacovia – a tomb of souls: „But perhaps that is my purpose, Master: / To robotize humans on earth / I always look forward to tomorrow / Like another tombstone.”

With Ștefan Baciu, the well-known goodness of the psalmist was returned, without expressing any novelty compared to what was known. But with Lucian Blaga, the tone and atmosphere change completely.

If I dared to make a comparison between the Argezean and the Blagian psalms, I could not decide which are more beautiful. Those of Arghezi for the boiling that consumes the verse and blows a cascade in the soul or the quiet, but extremely suggestive, plasticizing ones of Blaga?

Arghezi's psalmist is bold, he demands accountability, but the Blagian passes like a cherub, with small but significant steps. „When you pass without sandals under the linden, pigeons, asleep on good eaves they wake up, believing that your footsteps, small, are seeds thrown a good hand for them.”

Modeling the Argezean tragedy, Blaga calms him down and transforms the search, still burning into a persevering one, but calm with elegiac tones.

The Blagian psalms are a fraction superior to the Argezean ones, perhaps by cosmicizing the lyrical atmosphere. The fight is not given exclusively on earth and only by the psalmist, it seems a given fight of divinity to recover the position in the microcosm of the human body, a forced fight being sought by: „In thorns here show yourself Lord. / Let me know what you expect from me.” [4, p. 239]

God is not denied, but his loss is acutely felt; the world of the Blagian psalms is a world that God went through, but left it. God is a dumb Identity, and the artist is sent into the light „to sit bent over the questions of the world” (*Letter*): „Where you fell from the broken world. You who sometimes' / Did you choose in front of me like the sun in the sea ...?” (*Psalm 151*).

The divine silence is in fact a preservation of the sacred, through which the poet's attributes are equal to those of God, but this is possible only through love, a theme capitalized in the *Psalm* in the volume *Song of Fire*: „Loving, we trust that we are. When we love / no matter how deep the night / we are in day / we are in you, Elohim.”

It is the same love that the Holy Apostle Paul preaches, Father Dumitru Stăniloae, but also Vasile Voiculescu in *Sonnets*, it is the same love invoked in the *Psalm of Love*, from *Posthumous*, where the tear (suggested by mourning and loneliness) is present, the tear symbol of the being, but also the representation of nostalgia for the „lost paradise.” [4, p. 156]

Is it a subtle reproach addressed by Blaga to the divinity, the same one we find in Ovidiu Papadima in his psalm, of course, in the earthly sphere? Known

only as an assiduous researcher, Ovidiu Papadima also sporadically publishes verses, and the ones that caught my attention were those published in the magazine *The Thought*, in issue 9, from 1931.

Titled simply *Psalm*, the poem depicts a singer of man's regrets, who struggles between possibility and helplessness, between limit and infinity: „Lord, why in Your hand / And in the dream made by my hand / Why did you plant me so crookedly? / I wanted steel, you made me out of lead ...

Surprisingly in a pleasant way, the poet describes by enumerating the human weaknesses, which in the flight to the stars of the being, resemble lead on wings and helplessness. The contrast between what man wants and what he can really accomplish is presented suggestively and realistically: „I would like to be with you only on the rocky peak, / But you are too high and the valley is too deep ...”

Although the aspiration is unlimited, the poet knows his condition and resigns himself to the unfinished stage, as one of the pendulum hypotheses between sin and innocence, between body and soul, says: „You only gave me the torment of a ship / Floating eternally between earth and sky.”

Doomed to eternal uncertainty and subject to sin, we exist against our will. The tear is the only relief given to us, a reflection of the divine tear illustrated in the *Psalm* of E. Manu, which continues to sing in the same lamenting tone: „God, give the flowers more life / And grow in every thought, / We understand you, God, still crying / Under big autumn skies and fog. / We gather the dew of Thy tears, / In the dream we are trying to suffer / In the flowers we love / He sings to his cherubim.”

If Bacovia dedicated a psalm to his girlfriend, why not write a psalm dedicated to pain? This is what Lucia Mihnea does, in the poem entitled *Psalm for my pain*, with which she is present in Emil Pinteas's collection – *The thought* – literary anthology. The nostalgia present in his verses springing from the passage of time and the ephemerality of being and places, which can nevertheless be revived through ritual movements and processes: „It simply came to our notice then / like then, / at the side of the road / with all the coolness around - / I would hear the voice of the dying hay / and in the glory that would rise / I would say psalms for my sorrow.”

Her psalm relates to sacred gestures by which, according to Mircea Eliade's theory, if they are made in a certain time and a certain place, they can bring the sacred back into the midst of the profane, the sacred being universal time, objectively revived on the occasion of communicating important historical

events., such as the sacrifice of Jesus. This is also the poet's goal, to revive the past and to immortalize it through her tears and pain.

Simion Cuboltă creates psalms in the manner of Ștefan Baciu, that is, in a priestly style. His presence in one of the anthologies of religious poetry, called the poems of Romanian Christians, says it all. He is a classic, ordinary psalmist, he is a bit more rhythmic, but without worries or dramas: „Deliver me, O Lord, from sin; / hinder the enemy, the accursed / strain my love, make my gardens flourish / and exalt me, O Lord, and believe me; / with the second birth – agree – me, / to be able to sing your glory with the angels / even in this valley of complaint.” (*Psalm*).

But I can't go to the end of my work without mentioning a recent discovery of mine in the religious journey made through Romanian literature: Shaul Carmel. Coincidentally, taking the volume on the library shelves in my hand and flipping through it, a title came to my mind: *Al Ihashev Et Panai (Prayer III)* in translation *Do not turn your back on me* (Kings, Book I, chap. 20), from page 123, from the volume *Dor de Dor*. In this volume the author has two psalms: *The Devil from Heaven, My Flowing Waters*.

In *The Devil in Heaven*, the wandering poet deals with the primordial struggle between good and evil, demon and divinity, hatred and love, expressing his feelings in short verses (2-3 words) in which the meaning must be caught between the lines: „Hell / It steals your greatness, / Your creatures / The fruits of paradise, / The sin of knowledge / Sublime.”

At the same time claiming that in man there is a dark side coexisting with the bright one, he cries helplessly to the sky: „Lord, my God, / God of children, / The whole of heaven.”

My flowing waters is the second psalm and betrays its assimilated culture, through the adopted tone – a tone present in Jeremiah's complaints at the ruined wall of Jerusalem.

Two stories intertwine in the poet: the history of the nativity and the history of the adoptive land: „blessed / Either – Your flame / Almighty, / Which lasted me, / It coagulated me / From the clay of bondage, / Of the chernozem of Moldova / Bathed by the Prut. / Blessed / Let the wind [...] / which snatched me / from there / and winged me / to fly, / In the years of ripe fruit, / To the sands of liberation / Bathed by the Nile.”

If the homeland meant for him a spiritual stagnation, the unfettered and native civilization of Egypt, of Israel, meant the land of promise, illustrated thus by the remembrance of the name of Moses: „Blessed sons, / Merciful, / That you left me / To enter / In

the promised land, / And not to die / Like Moses / So I can sing [...] / Increase the, / Hallowed be / Your name / Great!"

Although the whole volume retains the same tone and writing style, I selected these two psalms that interested me for these articles.

Of course, a lot of psalms are hidden under titles like prayer, hymn, praise or glorification, but the intention was clearly expressed by following only those creations that bear the title of the psalm.

Naive or daring, blaming or praising, blessing or asking for mercy, literary or biblical psalms are among the most brilliant ornaments preserved in the sip of the priceless treasures of Romanian literature.

Shaped in a timid language or on the contrary philosophy, cryptic, obscure or even strange, this species were cultivated from Dosoftei to Doinaș taking the form of an incredible creations.

Asking myself once more what made the psalm an imposing and perpetual presence, I found the answer within me, materialized in the form of a phrase: faith in God.

This faith in God I wanted to teach my students and due to this type of literature I managed to awake their interest in old literature and I managed to create an implicate reader who loves to read in an involved manner.

Conclusions

- ✦ Romanian religious poetry, in which the psalm falls emotionally or only semantically (etymologically), has been cultivated since ancient times, and is the oldest literary species, educating the masses, inserting and maintaining the youngest religious thrills.
- ✦ The most prolific period from this point of view was that of the third and fourth decades of the last century, supported by the existence of the magazine *The Thought*.
- ✦ Although it was considered to be of a nationalist, extremist orientation, *The Thought* had the most interesting literary configuration, most of the important writers of the time publishing in its pages.
- ✦ Many of the titles published here are entitled *Psalms* and their authors, religious or less religious, diligently cultivate this literary genre.
- ✦ With roots deeply embedded in traditions, starting with biblical psalms, literary psalms are some of the most beautiful creations in our literature.
- ✦ As long as the Christian religion exists, the psalm will be cultivated, even if in addition to obedience, they express denial, rebellion or simply – tears and search, and this can be considered a method of educating religious and literary students' consciousness, from the most cruel ages.

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